

TIPS TO IMPROVE PRONUNCIATION AND SPEAK LIKE A NATIVE SPEAKER

Bahriddinova Nilufar Nasriddin qizi

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

the faculty of foreign languages

a third-year student

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Annotation: The article below is very helpful for every learner of English as it serves to help pronunciation

Key words: read aloud, stress in words, a well-written text, revise words, speaking practice

1. Read aloud

Mix business with pleasure: Read and improve your English pronunciation.

Reading aloud is actually the same as speaking practice. Only you speak not with the interlocutor, but with yourself, besides, you do not need to invent a speech - there is a book with a well-written text in front of you. Therefore, read aloud whenever possible.

2. Read slowly but correctly

Reading at speed was relevant only in elementary school in literature lessons. When reading an English-language book out loud, try to pronounce each letter clearly, put stress in words correctly, read slowly but clearly.

3. Watch your intonation

If you have such an opportunity, turn on the audiobook, listen to where the carrier makes logical accents and pauses, place the signs of increasing and decreasing intonation in the text. Then turn off the recording and try to copy the intonation and pronunciation of the carrier based on your notes. And besides that, use our guide "Intonation in English: Rules and Techniques for Learning."

4. Read aloud

Another useful exercise to help you improve your English pronunciation. Find an audiobook and text to it (or just an audio recording with text). Start recording and try to read the text along with the speaker, imitating his manner of speaking. The first couple of pages you can do this "to yourself", and then, when you already "feel" the pronunciation, start reading aloud.

5. Read to a friend or a teacher

If you are studying with an English teacher, then you are probably doing the reading exercises. Take your time while reading, the teacher does not expect high speed from you. Read as clearly as possible, then the teacher will be able to catch mistakes in your speech and explain to you how to get rid of them. If you are studying on your own, find a "colleague" among your friends who knows English about your level. Read different texts together, try to find and correct each other's mistakes.

6. Check the dictionary

As you read, you will come across unfamiliar words. We always advise you to guess their meaning from the context, from the article "A language guess is your assistant in learning English" you will learn how to develop this useful skill and use it in practice. But the

pronunciation must be checked with the dictionary if you are not sure that you know how to pronounce a word correctly. It is best to use an online dictionary where all concepts are voiced by native speakers. For example, the Merriam-Webster Dictionary or the Oxford Dictionaries.

7. Record your voice

While reading the text, try recording your voice on a dictaphone (such an application is available in any smartphone). Listen to the recording and compare your sound with the voice acting of the carrier. We want to warn you that the voice recording will sound, to put it mildly, unusual. In the early stages of learning English, you can even experience a real shock at the difference between how you usually hear yourself and what people hear, between you and a native speaker. Do not worry, this is not yet a reason for despondency: such an entry is not evidence of your shame, but a new reason to work further on your knowledge and emphasis. Try to find inaccuracies in pronunciation yourself, think about how natural the speech sounds, how accurate your intonation is, etc. In the next lessons, try to get rid of your accent.

8. Choose the "right" books

Pick a fascinating book from the sea of literature and start improving your pronunciation today.

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Your classes should evoke positive emotions, so we advise you to take your literature selection seriously. We recommend that you familiarize yourself with our articles "What books to read in English. How to read them correctly" and "Is it useful to read adapted books in English?". From them you will learn how to choose the right book for you.

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